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DE-RISK Project

D3.5 Democratizing the RES investments: DE-RISK crowdfunding campaign

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AML	Anti-Money Laundering
BP	Business Plan
CE	<i>Comunidad Energética</i> (Energy Community)
CNMV	<i>Comisión Nacional del Mercado de Valores</i> (Spanish Financial Conduct Authority)
CSP	Crowdfunding Service Provider
D	Deliverable
DD	Due Diligence
EE	Energy Efficiency
ECSP	European Crowdfunding Service Provider
ECSPR	European Crowdfunding Service Provider Regulation
ESMA	European Securities and Markets Authority
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EU	European Union
FCA	Financial Conduct Authority
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IBAN	International Bank Account Number
IoT	Internet of Things
KIID	Key Investment Information Documents
KIIS	Key Investment Information Sheet
KYC	Know Your Client
LFM	Local Flexibility Markets
M	Month
ROI	Return on Investment
SEPA	Single Euro Payments Area
T	Task
UBO	Ultimate Beneficial Owner
VAT	Value Added Tax
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the deliverable **D3.5: Democratising the RES investments: DE-RISK crowdfunding campaign** of the Horizon Europe project DE-RISK — *The adoption of Local Flexibility Markets (LFM) to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems* (funded under Grant Agreement No. 101075515). It highlights the results achieved under the task **T3.4: Financial schemes: funding the customers journey to participate in LFMs and democratising its access** (M1-M36), led by ECROWD with contributions from all Consortium partners.

The main focus of this deliverable is to outline the legal framework and the specifics of launching the locally-focused crowdlending campaign related to the Murcia pilot project of DE-RISK, that is correspondent with the milestone **M55: Crowdfunding Campaign Launched** of the project.

It is also described that, during the initial period of the Task T3.4 of the project, there has been prior experience gained by launching two other crowdlending campaigns in Spain, where energy communities acted as borrowers of both collective loans, for which the funds were raised.

INTRODUCTION

Overview of the DE-RISK project

DE-RISK, whose acronym stands for “*DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems*” is a project funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement nº 101075515. DE-RISK aims to support the market uptake of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) by fostering the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs) and unlocking up to 100 GW of flexibility in 2030 which will allow a safe and reliable integration of RES in the grid. DE-RISK will achieve this ambitious objective by minimising the investments and implementation risk through an innovative consumer behaviour change journey that will increase end-users' trust and willingness to participate in the LFMs.

Description of the deliverable content, objectives and purpose

Under the WP3 “Regulatory, Policy, Financial State of the Art Analysis” and the task T3.4 “Financial schemes: funding the customers journey to participate in LFMs and democratising its access”, the scope of this deliverable D3.5 is to provide detailed description of the process for launching a crowdlending campaign oriented to raise funds from local investors to LFM and EE projects such as the four pilots included in the DE-RISK project.

Although the aim of this deliverable is to explain the specific crowdlending campaign launched for the Murcia Spanish pilot of the DE-RISK project, the objective is also to prove that this financial mechanism is suitable to fit the needs of energy communities. Following this objective, the details of two other crowdlending campaigns that were launched during the previous months of the T3.4 (August 2023 and April 2024) are also explained.

Methodology:

- Description of the crowdlending and its EU legal framework for the activity of the crowdfunding platforms: the European Crowdfunding Service Providers Regulation (ECSPR).
- Listing the phases of a crowdlending campaign.
- Description of the experience gained along with the task T3.4 with the launch of two crowdlending campaigns that gave priority to the network of the borrower’s local energy community as their preferred investors.

- Detailed explanation of all steps and activities done for the launch and completion of the crowdlending campaign related to the Murcia Spanish pilot of the DE-RISK project.

Relation to other activities

Since the previous deliverable **D3.4: Financial schemes: funding the customer journey via traditional and innovative mechanisms** developed the idea that the deployment of LFM needs non-traditional mechanisms for financing assets like metering devices or RES, this D3.5 is focused on describing the detailed implementation of a crowdlending campaign as an effective, innovative and participative mechanism for raising funds needed for LFM, RES and Energy Efficiency (EE) investments of projects like the four pilots of the DE-RISK project itself.

The objective of the campaign in this deliverable is directly related to the Murcia Spanish pilot project, which was detailed in related deliverables under **WP4: Case study preparation, implementation and validation**, such as **D4.1: DE-RISK Case studies characterization and data collection plan**, and **D4.4: Implementation and operation for DE-RISK Case Studies**.

This campaign is also a part of the exploitable result number **ER07** described in the deliverable **D5.2: DE-RISK identification and assessment of exploitable results** in the **WP5: Local Flexibility business models, exploitation and replication**.

This deliverable also references the results of the question included in the previous deliverable **D2.2: Data collection and analysis** that measures the citizen willingness to invest in crowdlending or crowdfunding campaigns in a close or distant area of the citizens' residence, similar to those described in this deliverable (please see Appendix).

The dissemination of both the launch and the achievement of the crowdlending campaign's goals is part of the activities under **WP6: Wide and High Impact Communication, Dissemination and Market Engagement**.

Part 1. The crowdlending and its legal Framework in the EU

The concept of crowdlending

Under the crowdlending financial mechanism (also known as Peer-to-peer lending or Debt crowdfunding), the crowd lends money as a debt to a company or other legal entity with the understanding that the money will be repaid with interest under the terms of a collective loan contract. It can look similar to traditional borrowing from a bank, but the legal entity borrows funds from lots of investors that can be both individuals or any kind of legal entity. But indeed, the main difference is that crowdlending offers **financial traceability of the money** consciously lent by the investors and received by the borrower. Thus, the borrower will know in detail the provenance of the funds received, which is not possible at all among traditional banking mechanisms.

Since crowdlending is a financial lending activity that puts investors and borrowers in contact, it is a fully regulated activity within the European Union (EU) under the regulation and control of the European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA)¹ and the national financial authorities.

The EU dcrece 2020/1503

Crowdlending service providers are nowadays authorised in the EU under the regulation 2020/1503².

As part of the EU's broader effort to regulate financial technology, the European Crowdfunding Service Providers Regulation (ECSPR) establishes a uniform legal framework for crowdfunding platforms operating in the European Union. It aims to harmonise rules between member states and improve the transparency and security of crowdfunding investments, so it applies to projects such as the crowdlending campaign we are describing.

¹ <https://www.esma.europa.eu/>

² REGULATION (EU) 2020/1503 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 7 October 2020 on European crowdfunding service providers for business, and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/1129 and Directive (EU) 2019/1937, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32020R1503>

The key-elements of the ECSPR are:

Authorization and Supervision

Crowdfunding platforms must be authorised by national regulators and comply with rules regarding governance, risk management, and transparency.

Investor's Protection

The regulation introduces different protection measures based on the investor type (retail or sophisticated investors), ensuring that investors are aware of the risks involved. For retail investors, platforms are required to carry out an appropriateness test to assess their knowledge and experience.

Cross-border Transactions and Campaigns

The ECSPR allows crowdfunding platforms to operate across EU borders with a single licence, enabling them to offer their services throughout the EU without needing to apply for authorization in each country individually.

Disclosure Obligations

Platforms must provide Key Investment Information Documents (KIID) that outline the main characteristics of the investment opportunities, including risks, to ensure transparency and informed decision-making by investors.

Default and Exit Plans

Crowdfunding platforms must have plans in place for orderly exit strategies in case of platform failure, ensuring that funds and investments are adequately protected.

Part 2. Key phases of a crowdlending campaign

Preparation and Planning

The legal entity that needs to raise the funds must have a project and a budget, and its expected timeline of execution. With this objective decided, the project promoter must get in touch with the optimal crowdlending platform for its crowdlending campaign.

Borrower agreement: Funding request

Once the project promoter and the crowdlending service provider (CSP, the owner of the crowdlending platform) have contacted and identified their mutual interest, a contractual agreement (funding request) is usually signed. Along with this agreement:

- The borrower and the crowdlending platform, and the individuals who are legally authorised to represent them, are identified.
- It is explicitly stated that the promoter is seeking funding through the CSP platform for his project.
- The legal and material capacity of the platform to provide a crowdlending service is asserted.
- A period of time is agreed during which the platform will request information and documentation from the borrower and the project in order to carry out its Due Diligence (DD) process.
- The detailed economical offer to the potential investors and the rates applicable to the platform are both definitively fixed.
- Following a favourable outcome of the DD process, the platform is duly authorised to publish the project the promoter is seeking funding for on its website and to proceed with the collection of funds.
- It is stated that, before the launch of the project on the platform, the borrower is required to provide the standardised information sheet “Key Investment Information Sheet (KIIS)” to be available in the platform for potential investors.

The compilation of borrower and project documentation

The main documents usually asked to be provided by the borrower during the DD process, when the borrower is a private company are:

- Balance sheet and profit and loss account at the end of last year and also at the last completed quarter.
- Last 2 full audit reports (if applicable).
- Report of the company's assets and activities (business lines, main customers and suppliers, etc.) and business forecasts for the next few years.
- Detailed list of all loan and other credit lines, from banks and from other types of financing mechanisms, with detailed monthly payment, the outstanding capital and the final maturity.

When the borrower is an energy community, a detailed Business Plan (BP) of its forecasted activities is requested.

Regarding the project to finance, the main documents asked are:

- Technical Project and its budget.
- Administrative permissions required to construct or install.
- Documents related to any public grants the project may have applied for or been awarded.

DD: A comprehensive exam of the documentation received, encompassing technical, legal, and financial analyses

The following aspects should be taken into consideration when conducting a technical analysis of the project to be financed:

- Technical Viability
- Regulatory Compliance
- Operational Efficiency
- Environmental Impact

The following aspects should be taken into consideration when conducting a legal analysis of the borrower to be financed:

- Corporate Entity Verification
- Ultimate Beneficial Owners (UBO) declared
- Management and Board Structure
- Compliance with Laws and Regulations

The following aspects should be taken into consideration when conducting a financial analysis of the borrower to be financed:

- Financial Statements Analysis
- Debt and Leverage Ratios
- Liquidity and Solvency
- Profitability Metrics
- Credit History and Existing Debt

The outcome of the DD process

If the outcome is favourable:

The CSP proceeds with the publication of the project on the platform.

If the outcome is unfavourable:

The promoter will be notified and the borrower agreement (funding request) will be terminated.

The preparation and subsequent launch of the campaign

Activities to be undertaken:

- KIIS redaction and subsequent validation of its content by the promoter.
- Publishing the project on the platform, including the KIIS document, at potential investors disposal.

In addition, these other activities are recommended:

- Arranging a physical and/or online campaign presentation event, where the borrower representatives explain the project and the crowdlending platform managing team details how to invest in it.
- Press release, both for local and specialised media.
- Mailing addressed to both the borrower and platform contacts (according to the opening phase's project).

- Social post on social media by the promoter and the platform (according to the opening phase's project).

Procedure for registration and fundraising from investors

- Register as an investor: Those persons willing to invest in a project published on the platform are required to complete a preliminary registration process, which entails creating a user profile and password, accepting the platform's general conditions and mandate, and answering two forms: one concerns to basic financial questions -which will need to be updated every two years- while the other is focused to determine the investor's capacity to bear losses -which will need to be updated every year-.
- In order to be accepted as an investor on the platform, it is compulsory to provide official identity documents (in the case of natural persons) or legal documents to attest the constitution of the company and the UBO ownership declaration (in case of legal persons). The aforementioned documentation must then be validated and accepted through a Know Your Client (KYC) process, which will be carried out by the platform itself or by the services of a specialised supplier. During the KYC process, the authenticity of the documentation provided will be validated under the Anti-Money Laundering (AML) regulation.
- Mechanisms for investment and contribution of funds: The most prevalent methods for investors to disburse funds are bank transfer and card payment. In the transfer payment case, the platform will provide precise instructions regarding the details that must be reported to the bank's website used for sending the transfer. In the case of a card payment, the investors will be redirected to a specialised gateway to complete the transaction. In both cases, it will be mandatory for the account holder or cardholder to be the same person on whose behalf the investment is being made.

Fundraising investors phases

In a "Km0" crowdlending campaign, where the participation of local (or engaged) investors is a priority, two or more consecutive phases for its opening to the potential investors can be established. These phases will progressively expand, in accordance with the principles of the "Km0" initiative. The aforementioned phases may be defined as follows:

- The initial phase of the project will be accessible only to those who are residents of the city, or also for those invited by the borrower as members of its network.

- The second phase will expand the investment opportunity for individuals in the county or province.
- The third phase will then expand the investment opportunity to the people of the whole region or state.
- The final phase will be open, accessible to all people of the country (or the entire EU) interested to contribute.

The duration of each phase will be agreed between the borrower and the ECSP, prior to the opening of the campaign on the platform.

During all the process, the CSP platform will act accordingly to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)³ regarding the personal data of the people that invest in the crowdlending campaign.

Loan formalisation procedure

After the fundraising campaign successfully ends and the targeted funds are collected, the following steps are:

- Drawing up a collective loan contract, in which the ECSP company (owner of the platform) - acting as legal representative of the investors inscribed in the campaign -, and the borrower will appear. This contract will also set out the specific terms and conditions of the loan, with a comprehensive schedule of repayments and a detailed list of the investors who have contributed to the collective funding.
- The loan signature may be ratified with a notary (under the Spanish-specific regulations) if the platform deems it necessary.
- Once the loan has been duly signed, the funds raised are given to the borrower, who must justify that they have been used for the agreed purpose.

Loan invoicing procedure

Once the loan agreement has been signed and formalised, the crowdlending platform collects the instalments from the borrower (usually on a monthly basis) through a duly authorised payment gateway, either via a SEPA (Single Euro Payments Area) direct debit or upon a wire transfer from the borrower to the platform's IBAN (International Bank Account Number)

³ https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/data-protection-eu_en

account. The platform will then manage every repayment back to all the investors that lent money to that collective loan.

It is important to note that since the borrower company pays interest to the investors in its collective loan, it is legally obliged to withhold a percentage of the interests corresponding to each investor and to pay these amounts to the relevant tax authority. In the case of Spain, this withholding tax percentage is currently 19%.

Part 3. Testing crowdlending campaigns for energy communities

During the previous months of the task T3.4 of the project, there has been prior experience of launching two other “Km0”-focused crowdlending campaigns in Spain, in August 2023 and April 2024, with energy communities acting as the borrower of both collective loans. An abstract of these two campaigns is as follows:

CE Luco Energía (Teruel, Spain)

Project borrower: **SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA LUCO ENERGÍA**. It is a non-profit consumer cooperative, legally operating as an energy community. It is located in the hamlet of Luco de Jiloca, in the province of Teruel, Region of Aragon, Spain.

The project to be financed was the extension of the collective solar energy installation of the energy community, costing €25,000.

The campaign was implemented through the ECROWD’s Crowdlending Service Provider platform, licensed by the Spanish Comisión Nacional del Mercado de Valores (CNMV)⁴ acting as the national Financial Conduct Authority (FCA).

The specific internet page of the fundraising campaign was:

[Comunidad Energética Luco de Jiloca - Teruel](#)

□ <https://www.ecrowdinvest.com/en/details/lucoenergia2>

⁴ <https://www.cnmv.es/portal/consultas/servicios-financiacion-participativa/proveedor.aspx?nreg=17&nif=B66143736&lang=en>

Minimum investment amount per person: €50

Maximum investment per person: in order to increase the number of investors supporting the project, a maximum amount of €1,000 per person was set.

Crowdfunding campaign's first phase: During the first two weeks of the campaign, only people invited by LUCO ENERGÍA energy community could invest through a special email link. In this phase, a total of 12 investors from their network participated with a total of €10,450 (average inversion of €870 per person).

Crowdfunding campaign's second phase: The opportunity to invest was then open to anyone else who wished to support the project. In this second phase, 39 investors participated with a total of €14,550 (average inversion of €373 per person).

Start date of the crowdfunding campaign: August 1st, 2023.

Date of achievement of 100% of the fundraising objective: August 18th, 2023.

Date of formalisation of the collective loan: August 25th, 2023.

The screenshot shows the Ecrowd! website interface. The top navigation bar is purple with the Ecrowd! logo and links for LOGIN, REGISTER, and EN. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with links for HOME, PROJECTS, HOW DOES IT WORK?, EVENTS, BLOG, PROJECT DETECTIVE, and FINANCE MY PROJECT. The main content area features the campaign title 'Ampliación de la Comunidad Energética de Luco de Jiloca - Teruel' and a 'Community' tag. A large image shows a solar panel array in a rural landscape, with the LUCO ENERGÍA logo and 'Km 0' and '€' icons. To the right of the image, the campaign details are listed: STATUS: SIGNED, AMOUNT: 25.000€, YEARLY INTEREST: (blank), MONTHLY INSTALMENTS: € 60, and INVESTORS: 51. A progress bar at the bottom of this section is filled to 100%. Below the image, the location is 'LUCO DE JILOCA, ES' and the developer is 'SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA LUCO ENERGÍA'. A 'Share' button is located at the bottom right of the campaign details.

Image of the URL home page of this crowdfunding campaign

CE Foios (Valencia, Spain)

Project borrower: **SAPIENS SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA**. It is a non-profit consumer cooperative, also operating as a group energy communities. Its activities spread along the region of Valencia, Spain.

The project to be financed was the collective solar self-consumption energy installation of the energy community of the town of Foios, placed in the roof of the public school, with a budget of €65,000.

The campaign was implemented through the ECROWD's Crowdlending Service Provider platform, licensed by the Spanish CNMV authority.

The specific internet page of the fundraising campaign was:

[Comunidad Energética de FOIOS - Sapiens Energia](#)

□ <https://www.ecrowdinvest.com/en/details/cefoios>

Minimum investment amount per person: €50

Maximum investment per person: in order to increase the number of investors supporting the project, a maximum amount of €1,000 per person was set.

Crowdlending campaign's first phase: During the first two weeks of the campaign, only people invited by SAPIENS ENERGÍA energy community could invest through a special email link. In this phase, a total of 41 investors from their network participated with a total of €22,675 (average investment of €553 per person).

Crowdlending campaign's second phase: The opportunity to invest was then opened to anyone else who wished to support the project. In this second phase, 114 investors participated with a total of €42,325 (average investment of €371 per person).

Start date of the crowdlending campaign: April 15th, 2024.

Date of achievement of 100% of the fundraising objective: May 6th, 2024.

Date of formalisation of the collective loan: May 15th, 2023.

Ecrowd! LOGIN REGISTER EN ▾

HOME PROJECTS HOW DOES IT WORK? EVENTS BLOG PROJECT DETECTIVE FINANCE MY PROJECT

Comunitat Energètica de FOIOS - Sapiens Energia

Community

STATUS: **SIGNED**

AMOUNT : **65.000€**

YEARLY INTEREST:

MONTHLY INSTALMENTS: **18**

INVESTORS: **155**

100%

LOCATION: **FOIOS, ES**

DEVELOPED BY **SAPIENS ENERGIA COOP. V.**

Share ▾

Image of the URL home page of this crowdlending campaign

Part 4. Crowdlending campaign for the DE-RISK Murcia pilot project

Project to be financed by the crowd

The main objective of this crowdlending campaign was to increase the scope of the DE-RISK (Horizon Europe) project by incorporating a new home into the local energy flexibility pilot being carried out in Murcia (Spain).

The collective loan has been intended for MY ENERGIA ONER to install a photovoltaic self-consumption system in a home in Murcia, along with devices to monitor electricity consumption aiming to improve its EE and explore its participation in the local flexibility market.

Images from the URL of this crowdlending campaign

The borrower: MY ENERGIA ONER SL

MY ENERGIA ONER SL (whose brand is MIW) is an energy company founded in 2013 in Murcia (Spain), which has evolved from its beginnings as a traditional marketer to proactively address the emerging needs of consumers and the changing dynamics of the electricity market.

Thanks to a business strategy focused on constant investment in innovation, it offers energy solutions that provide improvements in service quality and greater autonomy to the consumer, who is increasingly demanding and committed to environmental sustainability.

The company is specialised in the marketing of electricity and photovoltaic self-consumption systems, maintaining the focus on offering a quality and transparent service in dealing with the customer. Among the services it includes the representation of renewable energy producers in the energy markets, development of energy communities, and energy services based on innovation, operating throughout the territory of mainland Spain.

The company participates in numerous innovation projects, which allow the company to be at the forefront of energy technology to provide solutions to consumers related to the energy transition, such as flexibility, aggregation and balancing services, prosumers, Internet of Things (IoT) for the control of energy assets or smart buildings, among others.

Image of the logo of the borrower company

Previous Funding Request Agreement and DD

As it is compulsory, MY ENERGIA ONER SL acting as the borrower, provided the requested information about the company and the project to finance, signed the funding request and validated the KIIS for the potential investors.

The legal advisors of Ecrowd previously prepared a specific funding request contract that was signed by both the borrower and the CSP. Also the risk advisors of Ecrowd validated the documents and information provided by the borrower.

The launch of the campaign

In order to engage as many local investors as possible, both the borrower and the CSP organised an informative webinar (in Spanish language) about the launch of the DE-RISK project and its crowdlending campaign.

There was a register sheet for the people willing to join the webinar:

Webinar:

10 de septiembre
19:00h
Online via Meet

Campaña de Crowdlending Km0 en Murcia

Ecrowd! **MIW ENERGÍA**

Inscripción al Webinar: Campaña de Crowdlending Km0 en Murcia

Te invitamos a asistir a la presentación online de la campaña de financiación participativa ciudadana local (crowdlending) para aumentar el alcance del proyecto europeo DE-RISK mediante la incorporación de una nueva vivienda al proyecto de flexibilidad energética local que se está llevando a cabo en Murcia.

Esta es una excelente oportunidad para los inversores locales de Murcia de formar parte de un innovador proyecto europeo, DE-RISK (<https://deriskproject.eu/>), destinado a la potenciación de los mercados locales de flexibilidad como herramienta para el despliegue masivo de las energías renovables y la eficiencia energética en nuestro parque de viviendas.

Fecha: Martes 10-09-2024

Hora: 19:00h - 20:00h

Reunión online: <https://meet.google.com/tki-mden-zsz>

Inscripciones abiertas (mediante este formulario)

Los datos personales de los asistentes podrán ser tratados por: ECROWD INVEST PLATAFORMA DE FINANCIACIÓN PARTICIPATIVA, S.L. B66143736, Av. Diagonal 477, 4a planta, 08036 Barcelona

Image of the register form for the webinar

During the webinar:

- Ricardo Perez-de-Zabalza (MIW) presented the Murcia-based company MY ENERGIA ONER SL acting as the borrower of the collective loan.
- Miguel Miñano (MIW) presented the DE-RISK project, its objectives, its pilots and its progress.
- Jordi Sole-Muntada (Ecrowd) explained the details of the crowdlending campaign and the mechanism to invest in the project.

Screenshots of the webinar about the launch of the campaign

The campaign was also disseminated through the social media accounts of the borrower and the DE-RISK project:

Image of a post in the DE-RISK account in Instagram

This campaign has shown an opportunity for local investors in Murcia and Spain to participate in the innovative European project DE-RISK, aimed at promoting local flexibility markets as a lever to boost the widespread deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency in the housing stock.

The campaign was implemented through the ECROWD's Crowdfunding Service Provider platform, licensed by the Spanish CNMV authority.

The specific internet page of the fundraising campaign is:

[DE-RISK Crowdfunding Campaign - Murcia \(Spain\)](https://www.ecrowdinvest.com/en/details/deriskprojectmurcia)

<https://www.ecrowdinvest.com/en/details/deriskprojectmurcia>

Image of the URL home page of this crowdlending campaign

Minimum investment amount per person: €50

Maximum investment per person: €300 (this maximum amount was set in order to increase the number of investors supporting the project).

Start date of the crowdlending campaign: September 10th, 2024.

During the first week of this crowdlending campaign (from September 10th to the 16th, 2024), investment in this collective loan was limited to residents of the city of Murcia. In this phase, a total of 6 local investors participated with a total of €1,500 (average investment of €250 per person).

In the following week of this crowdlending campaign (from September 17th to the 23th, 2024), investment in this collective loan was expanded to investors throughout the region of Murcia. In this phase, a total of 5 investors participated with a total of €1,250 (average investment of €250 per person).

Afterwards, in order to reach its target amount, the investment was open to anyone who wanted to participate and support the project. In this phase, a total of 17 investors participated with a total of €3,750 (average investment of €220 per person).

Description	Questions from investors	28 Investors	Project owner	Management team	Investment guide
Vicente 300€	Jesus 300€	Juana Teresa 300€	Jorge 300€		
Adria 300€	Iñaki 300€	Lucia 300€	Victoria 300€		
Raúl 300€	Alejo 300€	Miquel 300€	Tomas 300€		
Miguel Ángel 300€	Pablo 300€	Mamolo 300€	Francisco 300€		
Carlos 300€	Pablo 275€	Manuel 250€	Ricardo 225€		
Diana 175€	Oriol 100€	Rubén 100€	Daniel 75€		
Alex 50€	Gustavo 50€	Francisco 50€	Iñan 50€		

Image of the investors that contributed to this crowdlending campaign

Date of achievement of 100% of the fundraising objective: September 25th, 2024.

Date of formalisation of the collective loan: October 1st, 2024.

The dissemination of the campaign results

After the campaign reached the 100% of its objectives, the goal was disseminated by the DE-RISK project social media channels:

Image of a post in the DE-RISK account in Instagram

Following the issuance of a press release, several Spanish media outlets published articles about this campaign:

- ❑ Murcia Diario: <https://www.murciadiario.com/articulo/industria-energia/28-inversores-regionales-colaboran-proyecto-risk-flexibilidad-energetica/20240926112926115527.html>
- ❑ Murcia Economía: <https://www.murciaeconomia.com/art/97616/28-inversores-murcianos-impulsan-la-flexibilidad-energetica-con-el-proyecto-de-risk>
- ❑ Solar News: <https://www.solarnews.es/2024/09/26/residentes-murcianos-colaboran-en-la-flexibilidad-energetica-mediante-el-proyecto-de-risk>

CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides a detailed description of how crowdlending serves as an effective mechanism to raise funds for investments related to LFM and EE in private companies and energy communities.

In addition to outlining the steps of a real crowdlending campaign launched for funding the integration of a new household in the Murcia Spanish LFM pilot of the DE-RISK project, it explains the effective opportunity to prioritise the participation of local investors (“km0” or from the borrower’s network) among those who invested in the project.

The European Crowdfunding Service Providers Regulation (ECSPR) offers a robust and effective legal framework for utilising the crowdlending mechanism through CSP-licensed platforms within the EU.

As awareness and acceptance of the crowdlending mechanism grows among borrowers— as well as among investors who value sustainability, ESG, local investing, impact investing, and financial traceability— the potential for replicating this participatory funding model will likely enhance investments in LFM and EE.

APPENDIX

Results of the analysis made within the deliverable D2.2

Under the scope of the deliverable **D2.2: Data collection and analysis**, one question was included in the online survey about the willingness of the respondents to invest in a collective loan (crowdfunding) to finance the investments of an energy community.

This analysis, using the results in surveys in Spain, France, Portugal, Ireland and Türkiye discriminated the following scenarios: If the respondent is participating in it; if it is in a area geographically close to where the respondent lives; if it is on the respondent's country; and if it is outside the respondent's country.

Main findings of this survey are presented below:

- **France** is the country where most answers were low willingness to invest in a collective loan, regardless of the location of the energy community.
- **Ireland, Portugal, and Spain** present a similar result, with most respondents answering a moderate high willingness to invest in an energy community. However, these values decrease for the energy communities far from their location – especially outside their country.
- **Türkiye** is the country with higher willingness to invest in a collective loan to finance the investments of an energy community. However, for a community outside the respondents' country, respondents present divided opinions.

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